

Protein production of SLC27A2

ID: SP001H-3

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Protocol description

This protocol is used to purify SLC27A2 expressed in insect cells using detergent solubilization followed by Flag affinity purification and size exclusion chromatography

SLC27A2 (Acc. No: O14975)	
Construct	SPNS2_301_pD-INS3
Tag ID and position	N-terminal AVI and Flag tag
Cleavage of Tag	No
Sequence SPNS2_301 (In bold primary Protein sequence, C-terminal AVI-Tag (green) - Flag-tag (pink))	MDYKDDDDKGSGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGMLS AIYTVLAGLLFLPLLVNLCCPY FFQDIGYFLKVA AVGRRVRSYGKRRPARTILRAFLEKARQTPHKPFLFR DELT YAQVDRRSNQVARALHDHLGLRQGDCVALLMGNEPAYVWLWL GLVK LGCAMA CLNYNIRAKSLLHCFQCCGAKVLLVSPELQA AVEEILPSL KKDD VSIYYVSRTSNTDGIDSFLDKVDEVSTEPIPESWRSEVTFSTPALY IYTS GTTGLPKAAMITHQRIWYGTGLTFVSGLKADDVIYITLPFYHSAAL LIGI HGCIVAGATLALRTKFSASQFWDDCRKYNVTVIQYIGELLRYLCNS PQKP NRDRDHKVRALGNLGRGDVWRQFVKRFGDICIYEFYAATEGNIGF MNYA RKVGAVGRVNYLQKKIITYDLIKYDVEKDEPVRDENGYCVRVPKG EVGL LVCKITQLTPFNGYAGAKAQTEKKLRDVFKKGDLYFNSGDLLMV DHEN FIYFHDRVGDTRWKGENVATTEVADTVGLVDFVQEVNVYGVHV PDHE GRIGMASIKMKENHEFDGKKLFQHIADYLPYARPRFLRIQDTIEI TGTF KHRKMTLVEEGFNPAVIKDALYFLDDTAKMYVPMTEDIYNAISAKT LKL
Expression System	Sf9 cells
MW	73,450 g/mol

Materials

Biological materials:	
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 1M HEPES, pH7.5 (Applichem, Cat# A6916) ▪ 5M NaCl (Sigma, Cat# S6546) ▪ n-Dodecyl-b-D-maltopyranoside (DDM) (Anatrace, Cat# D310) ▪ cOmplete™, EDTA-free Protease Inhibitor Cocktail (Roche, Cat#04693124001) ▪ Anti-Flag M2 Affinity Resin (Sigma, Cat# A2220) ▪ Flag peptide (Sigma, Cat# F3290-25mg) ▪ TEV (Tobacco Etch Virus) protease (produced in-house) ▪ Superose 6 increase 10/30 GL (Cytiva, Cat#29-0915-96)
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dounce homogeniser ▪ Gravity flow columns ▪ 100 kDa cut-off centrifugal concentrators

Reagents setup

- 5 mg/mL Flag-peptide stock solution (dissolve in 10 mM HEPES, 150 mM NaCl, pH 7.5)

- 10% (w/v) DDM solution in H₂O (leave at 4 °C overnight to allow complete solubilisation and store at -20 °C)

Procedure

Expression

Expression Vector: SLC27A2_305_pD-INS3
Cell line: Sf9
Source: waver expression
Expression duration: MOI 1, 27°C for 72 hours

Purification

Cell disruption by Dounce homogeniser

Affinity purification with Anti-M2 affinity column

Buffer:

- Solubilization buffer: 50mM HEPES pH 7.5, 150mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, Benzoase, complete EDTA free, 1% DDM
- Equilibration/Wash buffer: 50mM HEPES pH 7.5, 150mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 0.026% DDM
- Elution buffer: 50mM HEPES pH 7.5, 150mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 0.026% DDM, 200µg/mL Flag peptide
- SEC buffer: 20mM HEPES pH 7.5, 150mM NaCl, 0.026% DDM

Method:

- Binding, wash and elution with Anti-Flag M2 gravity column
- Temperature: +4°C

Size exclusion chromatography

Buffer:

- SEC buffer: 20mM HEPES pH 7.5, 150mM NaCl, 0.026% DDM

Method:

- Column: Superose 6 increase 10/30 GL
- Flow rate: 0.5ml/min
- Fractions: 0.5ml
- Temperature: +4°C

Size exclusion chromatogram

Chromatogram overlay of 4 injections

Pooling SEC fractions B12 and C1

Coomassie stain analysis

Additional notes

Data availability

References

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.